

TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY AND PROFITABILITY OF CATFISH (*Clarias gariepinus*) PRODUCTION ACROSS POND CULTURE SYSTEMS IN PLATEAU STATE, NIGERIA

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<https://doi.org/10.70118/ajaas.032606010.05>

ABSTRACT

The study analysed the technical efficiency and profitability of Catfish production across pond cultures system in Plateau State, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 273 Catfish farmers across the concrete pond, earthen pond and plastic tank Catfish production models. Primary data were collected for the study with the aid of structured questionnaire. The data were analysed using Stochastic Production Frontier Model, Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) and Net Farm Income.

The technical efficiency result showed farmers under concrete pond and plastic tank cultures required about 4.1% and 2.4% efficiency improvement respectively to attain status of the most efficient farmer. Under the earthen pond culture however, the catfish farmers needed about 30% efficiency improvement to be fully efficient. Age, sex, marital status, farm records, education, farming experience and extension visit were the variables that significantly influenced technical inefficiency under concrete and earthen ponds respectively. The result further shows that the plastic tank culture has the highest net farm income (N314,196.54) among the three pond culture systems analysed in the study area. The one-way analysis of variance results showed significant difference ($p < 0.001$) among the Catfish production across pond culture systems. It is recommended, Plateau State Government should provide trainings and credit facilities to concrete and earthen pond Catfish farmers.

KEYWORDS: Technical efficiency; Profitability; Production; Catfish farmers; Pond cultures

INTRODUCTION

Available data from the World Development Indicators from 1981 to 2021 show that fish production in Nigeria grew from 0.058 million metric tons in 1981 to 1.08 million metric tons in 2021 (TrendEconomy, 2023). Similarly, between 1981 and 2021, fishery Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Nigeria increased from

N0.55 billion to N 2.23 billion. Among all non-plant protein sources, only fish can be raised in large numbers in a homestead, that is aquaculture (Ayuba et al., 2020). Belton et al.(2014) stated that aquaculture possess the potential to reduce poverty and enhance food security, especially among the low to middle class. Ahmadu et al.(2021) corroborated that aquaculture is considered

an important agricultural activity that is capable of ending nutritional deficiencies of the world and contributing to poverty reduction. Akegbejo-Samsons and Adeoye(2012) stressed that small-scale aquaculture does not require expensive equipment or structure as the resources needed could be recycled from the farm or surrounding.

More so, the aquaculture sub-sector is seen as crucial for achieving self-sufficiency in fish production and meeting nutritional needs. Fish farming, whether in earthen ponds, concrete, or mobile tanks, is considered an essential solution to meeting the rising demand for fish products (Okonji, 2021). Among the species of fish that have been cultured, Catfish is the commonest. According to Ahmadu et al.(2021), Catfish of the family *Clariidae* comprise the most commonly cultivated fishes in Nigeria. The favoured Catfish species in Nigeria aquaculture include: *Clarias gariepinus*, *Heterobranchus bidorsalis*, *Clarias* × *Heterobranchus* hybrid (*Heteroclarias*) and *Clarias nigrodigitatus*.

Aquaculture, like other agricultural production activities, Ahmed et al.(2021) reported that it requires the optimum combination of resources such as labour, fingerlings, feed, medicine, equipment, and land in order to obtain adequate yield. This is where the application of technical efficiency becomes handy. The most common output-oriented measure of technical efficiency is the ratio of observed output to the corresponding stochastic frontier output. According to Sujaya (2017) and Ume et al. (2020), this measure of technical efficiency takes a value between zero and one. It measures the output of the *i*-th firm relative to the output that could be produced by a fully-efficient firm using the same input vector. Clearly, the first step in predicting the technical efficiency, TE_i , is to estimate the parameters of the stochastic

production frontier model, which is based on Cobb-Douglas production function. The Cobb-Douglas production function combines constant, increasing and decreasing returns to scale, depending on the coefficient of elasticity (Degefa et al., 2017). This property makes it the most suitable functional form for production-related studies. Additionally, the model showcases the factors that increase or decrease inefficiency in a production enterprise (Ume et al., 2020). The application of technical efficiency to the production is the hallmark of this study, given the economic importance of Catfish production and the need to ensure optimum resource combination.

Interestingly, there have been attempts by the Nigerian government to expand the supply of fishery products in the country. Some of the programmes aimed at increasing fish production were: on-shore fisheries development project; National Accelerated fish production project (NAFPP) and Canoe mechanization scheme (CMS); Special fisheries development project and processing and marketing project. (FAO, 2020). Despite increasing adoption of pond culture systems, productivity differences suggest persistent inefficiency in Nigeria, and particularly, Plateau State. Fish production in general is impeded by low productivity, high mortality, water problems, high cost of feed and poor management practices (Nwosu et al. 2003; Amaefula et al., 2010). World Bank (2010) ascertained that, much work is still required in the fisheries sector of Nigerian economy, mainly in terms of capacity building, to raise fish farmers' productivity through improved management practices. This assertion by the World Bank is an obvious pointer to inefficiency that prevails in the fishery sector. Therefore, the desired growth in

Catfish production that will bridge the supply demand gap cannot be achieved without sound use of science and technology, embodied in efficient and cost-effective use of inputs in production.

Previous studies (Kareem et al., 2008; Nkamigbo et al., 2014; Olanrewaju, 2019; Idris-Adeniyi et al., 2021) have been made to analyse technical efficiency and profitability of Catfish farmers in Nigeria. However, an in-depth study on technical efficiency and profitability of Catfish production across pond culture systems has received less emphasis. For instance, there have been very few recent empirical reviews on Catfish farmers' perceptions and preferences on pond culture systems that are most economically viable. To the best of the knowledge of the researcher, no available study on analysis technical efficiency, technical inefficiency, and profitability of different pond cultures or production models in Plateau State. Hence, this study seeks to fill the identified gaps. This was done by finding answers to the following research questions: what is the technical efficiency of Catfish farmers across pond culture systems in Plateau State? what are the determinants of technical inefficiency across pond culture systems in Plateau State? and what is the profitability of Catfish production across pond culture systems in Plateau State? The general objective of the study was to analyse the technical efficiency, technical inefficiency, and profitability in Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) production across pond culture systems in Plateau State, Nigeria. The hypotheses statements of the study were, technical efficiency of Catfish produced across pond culture systems in the study area does not have any significant difference, technical inefficiency of Catfish produced across pond culture systems in the study area does not have any significant difference, and profitability of Catfish

production across pond culture systems does not have any significant difference. The outcome of the technical efficiency, and profitability from this study revealed areas of policy intervention that could help enhance the productivity of Catfish farmers and consequently alleviate their poverty. Invariably, the result of this study would assist extension agents in training Catfish farmers to improve profitability and optimum resource combination.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This study was conducted in Plateau State, Nigeria in 2024. The study area is located between latitude 08° 24'N and longitude 008° 32' and 010° 38' east. The State Comprises Seventeen Local Government Areas. These are Barkin Ladi, Bassa, Riyom, Jos East, Jos North, Jos South in Northern agricultural zone; Mangu, Kanam, Pankshin, Kanke and Bokkos in Central agricultural zone, and Langtang North, Langtang South, Mikang, Qua'anpan, Shendam, Wase in Southern agricultural zone (Shut, 2014). The State is divided into three (3) agricultural zones according to Plateau Agricultural Development Programme (PADP) which include: Central Zone with headquarters at Mangu, Southern Zone with headquarters at Yelwa, and Northern Zone with headquarters at Jos South.

The State enjoys tropical climate with two distinct seasons. These are the rainy season (April – October) and the dry season (November – March). Tropical forest exists in the South, while Guinea Savannah Occupies the northern peripheries. Plateau State has a near temperate climate suitable for aquaculture, and with an average temperature of between 13 and 22°C. The warmest temperatures usually occur in the

dry season months of March and April while the coldest weather is between December and February (Gambo *et al.*, 2017). The mean annual rainfall varies from 131.75cm in the Southern part to 146cm on the Plateau and the highest rainfall is recorded between the months of July and August. Farmers in Plateau State are also involved in aquaculture practices.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

The three (3) agricultural zones of Plateau State were used for the study. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed for the selection of respondents. Stage 1: Two LGAs were purposively selected from each agricultural zone based on cat fish production intensity as well as high concentration of active pond farmers. The LGAs were Jos North and Jos South from Plateau North, Langtang South and Shendam from Plateau South and Mangu and Pankshin from Plateau Central. Stage 2: This involved the purposive selection of three communities per LGA based on large number of active Catfish farmers and volume of production. Stage 3: The third stage utilized stratified sampling technique to segregate the Catfish farmers from each selected area into strata, namely, concrete ponds, plastic tanks and earthen ponds cat fish farmers. The reason was to get a homogeneous distribution of the sub-population. Stage 4: This was achieved using simple random sampling technique through the balloting method. Yamane (1967) and Bourley's formula were used to get the actual number of respondents based on the list of farmers obtained from the reconnaissance survey. The Yamane's formula was expressed as follows:

$$n = \frac{N^2 e^2}{1 + N e^2} \dots\dots\dots(\text{equation 1})$$

Where:

n = sample size.

N = Population of Catfish farmers = 855

e = margin of error = 0.05

The application of Yamane (1967) formula produced 273 respondents as the sample size for the study.

Bourley's formula was used to proportionately distribute the sample among the selected communities. The formula is as follows:

$$n_h = (N_h / N) \times n \dots\dots(\text{equation 2}).$$

Where:

n_h = sample size for each community

N_h = population of Catfish farmers in a community

N = population of Catfish farmers in the selected six local government areas

X = sample size for the study based on Yamane (1967) formula = 273

The detailed results from application of the Yamane (1967) and Bourley's formula are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Sample Size

Agricultural zone	LGA	Community	Fish farmers			Number of fish farmers randomly selected		
			Concrete pond	Plastic tank	Earth pond	Concrete pond	Plastic tank	Earth pond
Northern	Jos North	Tina Junction	33	31	1	11	10	1
		Gigiring	26	12	1	8	4	1
		Faringada	29	20	6	9	6	2
	Jos South	Kwang	33	20	2	11	6	1
		New Abuja Rayfield	29	15	2	9	5	1
			38	25	4	12	4	1
Central	Mangu	Sabongari	30	20	1	10	6	1
		AngwanTul	20	12	3	6	4	1
		Pushit Panyam	35	23	14	11	7	5
	Pankshin	Bot	20	11	2	6	4	1
		Tukung Duk	15	8	8	5	3	3
			14	11	2	5	1	1
Southern	Shendam	Shargang	2	25	25	1	8	8
		Ugwanrina Lakushi	3	15	22	1	5	7
			3	20	23	1	6	7
	Langtang South	Magama	2	15	30	1	5	10
		Taka-Lafiya Turaki	4	10	20	2	3	6
			4	15	40	2	5	13
6	18	340	309	206	111	92	70	

Source: Author's own Computation, 2024

Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire. Data collected include pond and tank size, price and quantity of feed, price and quantity of output, quantity of lime, quantity of fingerlings, and manday of labour used. The objectives of the study were achieved using Stochastic frontier models, and net farm income model, whereas the hypothesis was tested using F-Test.

Analytical Techniques

Specification of the Technical Efficiency Model

A stochastic frontier production function was estimated using maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) techniques to obtain farm specific technical efficiency and its determinants as follows:

$$Y = f(X\beta) e_i \dots\dots\dots (\text{equation 3})$$

Where:

Y = Weight of Catfish at table size (kg)

X_i = Vector of quantities of inputs used in Catfish production

β = Vector of parameters to be estimated

e_i = error term $e_i = v - u_i$ = composite error term

The v_i are random variables which account for random variation in output due to factors outside the farmers' control such as weather, disease and measurement error in production. It is assumed to be independently and identically distributed $N(0, \sigma^2_v)$ and independent of u_i .

$$TE = Y_i / Y_i^* \dots\dots\dots (\text{equation 4})$$

Where:

TE = Technical Efficiency, which ranges from 0 to 1.

Y_i = observed output

Y_i^* = frontier's output.

Using the Cobb-Douglas functional form, the implicit stochastic frontier model for Catfish production was specified as follows:

$$\ln Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_i \ln X_i + V_i - U_i \dots\dots\dots (\text{equation 5})$$

Where:

Y_i = Catfish output in Kg

β_0 = Intercept

β_i = Vectors of parameters to be estimated

X_i = Vectors of Inputs used in Catfish Production

The explicit stochastic frontier model for Catfish production was stated as;

$\ln Y = \beta + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + \beta_5 \ln X_5 + V_i - U_i$ ((equation 6) Where:

Y = Fish output (Kg)

X_1 = lime (kg)

X_2 = Fingerlings (number stocked)

X_3 = Labour (man days)

X_4 = Fish feed (kg)

X_5 = Pond and tank size (m^2)

V_i = Random shock variables

U_i = Non negative random variables

β = intercept $\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = unknown parameters to be estimated. V and U stand for the error components, with V iid N (0,) as stochastic noise, U iid N (0) as a measure of the inefficiency of the ith Catfish farmer.

V_i = Technical inefficiency effects

Ln = Natural logarithm

Technical inefficiency model

The study assumed that the technical inefficiency effects are independently distributed and U_{ij} arises by truncation (at zero) of the normal distribution with mean U_{ij} and variance, δ^2 . Thus, the technical inefficiency effects (U_{ij}) were defined by:

$$U_i = \delta_0 + \delta_1 \ln Z_1 + \delta_2 Z_2 + \delta_3 Z_3 + \delta_4 Z_4 + \delta_5 Z_5 + \delta_6 Z_6 + \delta_7 Z_7 + \delta_8 Z_8 + \delta_9 Z_9 \quad (7)$$

Where:

U_i = the technical inefficiency of the i-th Catfish farmer

Z_1 = Sex (1 = male, 0 = female)

Z_2 = Marital status (1 = married, 0 = single)

Z_3 = Household size (Number)

Z_4 = Age (years)

Z_5 = Educational qualification (Number of years of formal schooling)

Z_6 = Catfish farming experience (years)

Z_7 = Maintenance of farm record (1 = yes, 0 = Otherwise)

Z_8 = Frequency of extension agent's visit (Number of visits)

Z_9 = Amount of credit accessed (N)

δ_{1-9} = parameters to be estimated

The variances of the random errors, $\delta^2 v$ and that of the technical inefficiency effects $\delta^2 u$ and overall variance of the model δ^2 are related thus; $\gamma = \sigma^2 u / (\sigma^2 u + \sigma^2 v)$ and the ratio $\gamma = \delta^2 v / \delta^2$, measures the total variation of output from the frontier which can be attributed to technical inefficiency (Abiola et al., 2021; Umar et al., 2017).

Net farm income

The net farm income model was of the form:

$$NFI = TR - TC \quad \dots, \text{ (equation 7)}$$

Where:

NFI = Net farm income of Catfish produced in (₦)

TR = Total revenue obtained from the sale of Catfish.

TC = Total Cost

Where $TC = TVC + TFC$

TVC = Total variable cost of Catfish production in (₦)

TFC = Total fixed cost of Catfish production in (₦)

The fixed costs of Catfish production were depreciated using the straight-line method to obtain the actual value of the equipment per production cycle.

The formula is given as:

Straight line depreciation = $(\text{cost of the asset} - \text{estimated salvage value}) \div \text{estimated useful life of an asset}$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Technical efficiency of Catfish production

The efficiency obtained from Cobb-Douglas frontier model are presented in Table 2. A technical efficiency score of less than 100% implies that Catfish farmers produced below the maximum frontier output. The efficiency scores under concrete pond culture ranged between 74.1% and 99.9% with a mean score of 95.9% implying that Catfish farmers required about 4.1% efficiency score to attain the status of the most efficient farmers given this model. Under the earthen pond culture range, the most efficient farmer had a technical efficiency of 99.9% while the least efficient farmers had a technical efficiency of 59.4% with a mean technical efficiency of about 70%. The minimum technical efficiency value attained by plastic tank farmers was 80.5% while the

maximum technical efficiency attained was 99.1% and mean was 97.6% meaning that plastic tank farmers needed 2.4% improvement to be fully efficient. The mean technical efficiency scores of 95.9% for concrete pond and 97.6% for plastic tank indicate a good level of technical efficiency for the average farmer but the earthen pond farmers' result indicates fair technical efficiency score.

The technical efficiency scores imply that on the average, the farmers were able to achieve about 70% optimal outputs from a given set of inputs under given technology and needed about 30% efficiency score to be fully efficient. The three pond cultures posted higher efficient scores than the results of Penda *et al.* (2013), in a study conducted in Benue State, which revealed that the mean technical efficiency was 61.9% and Oguoma *et al.* (2010) in a study carried out in Imo State with a mean technical efficiency of 75.49%.

Table 2: Distribution of Technical Efficiency Scores

Efficiency range	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Minimum	Maximum
Concrete pond (n=111)					
0.7418-0.8048	2	1.80	0.96	0.74	0.99
0.8049-0.8679	3	2.70			
0.8680-0.9310	11	9.91			
0.9311-1.000	95	85.59			
Earthen pond (n=70)					
0.5938-0.6953	37	52.85	0.70	0.60	1.00
0.6954-0.7969	29	41.43			
0.7970-0.8985	2	2.86			
0.8986-1.000	2	2.86			
Plastic tank (n=92)					
0.8055-0.8519	1	1.09	0.98	0.81	0.99
0.8520-0.8984	0	0			
0.8985-0.9449	0	0			
0.9450-1.000	91	98.91			

Source: Field survey, 2024

F-statistics = 6.67 (>0.000)

Hypothesis testing 1:

The test was done with the aid of one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results, presented in Table 3 show that the mean technical efficiencies for concrete pond, earthen pond and plastic tank were 0.96, 0.70 and 0.98 respectively. The F-statistic (6.67) of the ANOVA was statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis. Consequently, there was significant difference in technical efficiency among Catfish production in the study area. In other words, the observed difference in the mean technical efficiencies of the various production models were not due to random errors. The difference was in favour of the plastic tank production model with the mean technical efficiency of 0.9760. Oluwatayo and Adedeji (2019) found that the plastic tank model had a higher mean technical efficiency than the earthen pond and which agrees with the findings of this study.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance of Technical Efficiency

Source	SS	DF	MS	F	Prob. >0.000
Between groups	0.0060420237	2	0.003020118	6.67	0.000
Within groups	0.122322952	270	0.000453048		
Total	0.128363	272	0.000472		

Source: Field survey, 2024

Mean technical efficiency for concrete pond = 0.96

Mean technical efficiency for earthen pond = 0.70

Mean technical efficiency for plastic tank = 0.98

Determinants of Technical Inefficiency

The Maximum likelihood estimates of determinants of technical inefficiency of Catfish production by concrete, earthen pond and plastic tank cultures are presented in Table 4. The sigma squared was statistically significant for all the production models (2.91, 4.65 and 4.48 for concrete pond, earthen pond and plastic tank respectively). This implies that the composite errors were correctly specified. According to Osman et al. (2018), the sigma squared indicate the correctness of the distributional form assumed for the composite error term. Baruwa & Omodara (2019) also held that a statistically significant sigma indicates a good fit and that the assumptions of composite error term distribution were specified correctly. This implies the Cobb-Douglas functional form is the best fit for the data.

The gamma ratio was also statistically significant for all the production models, indicating the presence of inefficiency effects in Catfish production. For the concrete production model, the coefficient of gamma (0.94) suggests that about 94% of the variations in the output of Catfish were due to the effects of technical inefficiencies while the remaining 6% could be attributed to other factors outside Catfish farmers' horizon of influence. For the earthen production model, the coefficient of gamma (0.80) suggests 10% could be attributed to other factors outside Catfish farmers' horizon of influence. For the plastic production model, the low coefficient of gamma (0.43) suggests that external factors or errors were responsible for technical inefficiencies.

The coefficients of the explanatory variables in the inefficiency model are of particular interest to this study. The positive signs of the parameters of the model for

concrete farmers implied that the associated variables increased inefficiency while the reverse is true for the negative signs. The coefficients of age, sex, and access to extension agents were positive. Their t-ratio were significant so the three variables contributed negatively to technical efficiency under the concrete pond culture. Thus, as age increases, farmers tend to be less productive. The contribution of age to technical inefficiency conformed to a priori expectation that as the fish farmers grew older, their technical efficiency would drop. This finding however, negated the findings of Esobhawan (2007) that age was a positive contributor to technical efficiency. Similarly, coefficient (0.16) of marital status was statistically significant and positive for only the concrete production model. The positive contribution of access to extension agents to technical inefficiency was the result of many farmers (45.71%) not having access to extension agents. Under the earthen pond culture, education and farming experience had negative coefficients and were significant (with coefficients of 0.04 and 0.01 respectively). Both variables contributed positively to technical efficiency of the fish farmers. An increase in the educational level of the respondents leads to a decrease in the inefficiency and vice versa. This result is expected because there is a connection between education and knowledge. Education means knowledge and it is expected to reflect in the manner that enterprises such as Catfish business are run. The positive contribution of farming experience was consistent with a priori expectation that business experience could be an indication of the practical knowledge acquired which enhance their business operations.

Table 4: Determinants of Technical Inefficiency

Variables	Concrete pond	Earthen pond	Plastic tank
Constant	(1.0887) (0.4451) [(2.4460)]**	0.7838 (0.0843) [9.2988]***	(0.0491) (0.2057) [(0.2389)]
Sex	0.3093 (0.1144) [2.7051]***	(0.0703) (0.0318) [(2.2117)]**	0.0162 (0.0366) [0.4424]
Marital status	0.1625 (0.0606) [2.6844]***	0.0113 (0.0345) [0.3287]	0.1980 (0.1748) [1.1328]
Household size	0.0043 (0.0095) [0.4543]	(0.0004) (0.0048) [(0.0933)]	(0.0294) (0.0297) [(0.9900)]
Age	0.0109 (0.0039) [2.7640]***	(0.0012) (0.0012) [(0.9848)]	(0.0027) (0.0030) [(0.9052)]
Education	0.0324 (0.0392) [0.8251]	(0.0364) (0.0177) [(2.0605)]**	(0.0764) (0.0504) [(1.5163)]
Catfish farming experience	(0.0035) (0.0052) [(0.6763)]	(0.0133) (0.0036) [(3.6478)]***	0.0112 (0.0098) [1.1462]
Farm records	(0.3898) (0.1626) [(2.3971)]**	(0.0378) (0.0270) [(1.3983)]	(0.0111) (0.0552) [(0.2002)]
Frequency of extension visit	0.0601 (0.0235) [2.5606]***	(0.0107) (0.0107) [(1.0048)]	0.0651 (0.0420) [1.5486]
Credit access	0.0781 (0.0477) [1.6361]	(0.0171) (0.0436) [(0.3927)]	0.0486 (0.0560) [0.8686]
Sigma-squared	0.0153 (0.0052) [2.9069]***	0.0043 (0.0009) [4.6471]***	0.0113 (0.0025) [4.4758]***
Gamma	0.9494 (0.0210) [45.1316]***	0.805 (0.0000) [6.8050]***	0.4342 (0.2004) [2.1674]**

Source: Field survey, 2024

Figures in round brackets () are Standard-error; figures in square brackets [] are t-ratio

Note: *** = significant at 1%, ** = significant at 5%

Profitability Analysis of Cat Fish

Production

The costs incurred and revenue obtained in Catfish production are presented in Table 5. The costs incurred and revenue generated were calculated using the prevailing prices at the time of the field survey. The fixed costs of Catfish production were depreciated using the straight-line method to obtain the actual value of the equipment per production cycle. The variable inputs were feed, fingerling, urea, lime and labour. The variable costs were calculated per square metre of pond for the production cycle of the three different cultures. The cost of feed in relation to total variable cost was 77.95% for concrete pond, 69.78% for earthen pond and 67.05% for plastic tank. This shows that cost of feed accounted for more than 65% of total variable cost regardless of the pond culture. The finding of Ugwumba and Chukwuji (2006) that cost of Catfish feed accounted for 73.56%.

The cost of fingerling was 21.51% of total variable cost for concrete pond, 25.56% for earthen pond and 28.69% for plastic tank culture is similar to the finding of this research work. The high cost is attributable to high price of fingerlings and inadequate supply to meet the growing demand for fingerlings and juveniles. The other variable inputs used contributed less than 5% of the total variable costs for the three pond cultures under study. The contribution of total variable cost and total fixed cost to the total cost of production were found to be 96.86% and 3.14% for concrete pond; 96.60% and 3.40% for earthen pond and 93.28% and 6.72 for plastic tank culture. The results indicate that total variable cost is the major cost incurred in Catfish production.

The result of Onyekuru *et al.* (2019), who

estimated the contribution of total variable cost and total fixed cost to the cost of Catfish production to be 86.58% and 13.42% respectively, in Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu State, Nigeria. Corroborated the findings of this study. Ashley-Dejo *et al.* (2017) reported that total variable cost contributed 86.6% while total fixed cost contributed 13.4% of the total cost of production in Oyo State. Also, Oluwasola and Ige (2015) observed that total variable cost contributed 96.66% and total fixed cost contributed 3.34% to the cost of Catfish production in Ibadan, Oyo State. Cost of feed has the largest percentage contribution to the cost of Catfish production in Nigeria. Most quality fish feed are imported and this contributes to high cost of fish feed and eventually, high cost of production. This finding agrees with Alawode and Oluwatayo (2019); and Ashley Dejo *et al.* (2017) research study. The implication of this is that fish feed is an important factor of Catfish production. In addition, if feed is not properly managed by the farmers and efficiently utilized by Catfish, it will have negative effect on profit (Robinson and Li, 2015). However, Edet *et al.* (2018) had a contrary observation. They reported that total variable cost contributed 42.86% while total fixed cost contributed 57.14% to the cost of Catfish production farming in Calabar metropolis, Nigeria. The average values of fixed costs were also analysed. Fixed costs are costs that last for more than one production cycle and do not change within one production period, but can be altered in the long run. The straight-line method was used to calculate the depreciation of this equipment. The items included fish pond, land, water pump, wheel barrow, fish net cover, feeders and aerators.

Table 5 shows that the average output of Catfish production per square meter was 56.9kg, 56.96 kg and 135.63 kg for concrete pond, earthen pond and plastic tank culture respectively. The corresponding unit selling prices were N2,795.05, N2,716.43 and N2,802.17 per kg of Catfish for concrete pond, earthen pond and plastic tank. The total revenue was calculated at N159,206.05, N154,727.85 and N380,058.32 for concrete pond, earthen pond and plastic tank respectively. The estimated gross margin per square metre (for the production cycle) of different pond cultures was N128,992.60 for concrete pond; N120,979.53 for earthen pond and N318,624.50 for plastic tank. The net farm incomes were N127,012.24 for concrete pond; N119,792.43 for earthen pond and N314,196.54 for plastic tank. This is consistent with the findings of Okpeke and Akarue (2015), who reported N384,306 as net farm income of fish farming business in Warri South Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. This implies that Catfish production is a profitable business for the three pond culture types studied. This observation also agrees with the findings of Ajagbe and Ojo-Fakuade (2019); Edet *et al.* (2018); Iruo *et al.* (2018); Ashley-Dejo *et al.* (2017) that Profit is the major, if not the sole factor that makes the business feasible. The value of benefit cost ratio (BCR), calculated as a ratio of total revenue to total cost was estimated to be 5.10, 4.43 and 5.77 for concrete pond,

earthen pond and plastic tank respectively. Therefore, the Catfish farmers benefits were N5.1, N4.43 and N5.77 for each N1 of costs respectively.

This further confirms that Catfish farming under the three pond cultures are profitable. Alawode and Oluwatayo(2019) reported BCR of 3.95 among Fish Farmers participating in Fadama III in Lagos state, Nigeria. Ashley-Dejo *et al.* (2017) reported a BCR of 1.69 among small-scale Catfish farmers in Oyo state, Nigeria. Tunde *et al.* (2015) reported BCR of 1.9 among fish farmers in Saki-East Local Government Area of Oyo state, Nigeria. Using the net farm income as a budgetary tool, Olawumi *et al.* (2010) found that both mono-culture and ploy-culture technologies were profitable in Ogun State, Nigeria. Idris-Adeniyi *et al.* (2021) also found that Catfish fish farmers in Osogbo metropolis, Osun State were able to break even from Catfish production and made profit with the benefit-cost ratio (BCR) of 1.5; and that the gross margin of fish farmers for a single farming season was N240,423.42.

The result shows that the plastic tank culture has the highest net farm income among the three pond cultures studied. This result varies with Oluwatayo & Adedeji (2019) who found that the earthen pond produced the highest net farm income in Lagos State Nigeria.

Table 5: Profitability Analysis of Cat Fish Production

1.	Variable Cost	Unit	CONCRETE POND			EARTHEN POND		
			Average Qty	Unit Price ₦	Cost/ m ² ₦	Average Qty	Unit Price ₦	Cost/ m ² ₦
i.	Feed	Kg	19.05	1,236.24	23,550.44	19.51	1,388.96	23,550.44
ii.	Labour	Man-days	0.256	285.30	73.05	0.74	312.11	230.96
iii.	Fingerlings	Number stocked	52	12,500.00	6,500.00	69	12,500.00	8,625.00
iv.	Lime	Kg	0.32	271.60	86.07	4.45	285.29	1,269.54
v.	Urea	Kg	0.36	10.81	3.89	2.14	34.29	73.38
2.	Total Variable Cost				30,213.45			33,748.32
3.	Fixed Cost (Depreciation)							
i.	Pond Construction	m ²	1		7.33	1	69.99	4.67
ii.	Plastic tank	m ²	-		-	1	-	-
iii.	Wheelbarrow	Numbers	1		3.01	1	59.91	1.99
iv.	Land	m ²	1		424.05	1	1,213.33	404.44
v.	Fish Net	numbers	1		31.08	1	359.26	359.26
vi.	Water Pump	numbers	1		393.38	1	3,388.89	388.89
vii.	Aerators	numbers	1		8.16	1	146.17	14.64
viii.	Feeders	numbers	1		11.04	1	66.17	13.23
4.	Total Fixed Cost				980.36			1,187.10
5.	Total Cost (VC+FC)				31,193.81			34,935.42
6.	Output/Prices	Kg	56.96	2,795.05		56.96	2,716.43	
i.	Revenue				159,206.05			154,727.85
7.	Total Revenue				159,206.05			154,727.85
8.	Gross Margin (TR-VC)				128,992.60			120,979.53
9.	Net Farm Income (TR-TFC)				127,012.24			119,792.43
10.	BCR				5.10			4.43

BCR = Benefit/Cost Ratio
F-statistics = 24.10 (p<0.001)

Hypothesis testing 2

The test was done with the aid of one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results as presented in Table 6 show that the mean net farm income for concrete pond, earthen pond and plastic tank were N127,012.24, N119,792.43 and N314,196.54 respectively. The F-statistic (24.10) of the ANOVA was statistically significant (p<0.001). Thus, the null hypothesis was

rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis. Consequently, there was significant difference in profitability among Catfish production in the study area. In other words, the observed differences in the profitability of the various production models were not due to random errors. The difference was in favour of plastic tank production model with net farm income of N314,196.54.

Hypothesis 2

Table 6: Analysis of variance of profitability

Source	SS	DF	MS	F	Prob. >0.000
Between groups	2.2037e+12	2	1.1018e+12	24.10	0.000
Within groups	1.2344e+13	270	4.571e+10		
Total	1.454e+13	272	5.348e+10		

Source: Field survey, 2024

C O N C L U S I O N A N D R E C O M M E N D A T I O N S

The plastic tank culture system presented a better comparative advantage over the concrete and earthen pond culture systems with the highest mean technical efficiency (97.6%) and net farm incomes (N314,196.54). It was recommended that Plateau State Government should provide

financial credit facilities and trainings to Catfish farmers under the concrete and earthen pond culture systems. Future research work should be carried out to determine the socio-economic characteristics and constraints to Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) production across pond culture systems in Plateau State should be conducted.

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